

RIGIDITY TUNABLE MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES FOR SOFT ROBOTICS

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Keywords: Rigidity Tuning, Multifunctional Composites, Soft Robotics

ABSTRACT

Soft robotics for human machine interactions requires development of new multifunctional materials that can adapt their physical properties, geometries and functionalities according to the environment they encounter. Among these, tunable rigidity is an important feature that is essential in allowing soft structures to become load bearing and perform mechanical work. Previous approaches for rigidity tuning typically demanded rigid and bulky supporting hardware for pneumatics, magnetic activation and heating, which are not suitable for soft robotics intended for human use. We have recently introduced methods for rigidity tuning in soft robotics that is directly powered with electrical current. This is accomplished with multilayered composites in which embedded elements are melted or softened through Joule heating. First we achieved four orders of magnitude change in tensile rigidity with embedded sheets of low melting point alloy. Activation times were on the order of 10-100s. For faster activation, we also designed and fabricated a conductive thermoplastic with low glass transition temperature that can be easily reached through joule heating of the thermoplastic. With a conductive thermoplastic elastomer we achieved rigidity tuning within seconds. The potential applications of these smart composites were demonstrated by incorporating them into a bio-mimetic soft robotic finger with multiple bending directions, which would otherwise be very complicated to fabricate and control.

1 INTRODUCTION

In natural organisms, reversible mechanical rigidity tuning allows soft limbs and members to support load and perform motor tasks. Organisms typically accomplish this with striated muscle tissue [1,2], hydrostatic skeletons [3], or catch connective tissue [4,5]. These natural materials and structures are lightweight and require fractions of a second to change their elastic rigidity by an order of magnitude. These properties are necessary for organism to perform mechanical work, support heavy loads, and control internal stress distributions while still soft and mechanically deformable in their passive state.

Mechanical rigidity tuning also has potential importance in bio-inspired robotics, wearable technologies, and other emerging domains of engineering. Previous attempts have involved external heating of shape memory polymers (SMP) for aerospace structures [6,7,8], hydraulic actuators for seismic response control [9,10], embedded heating of multilayered SMP composites [11,12], and electrostatic clamping of multilayered beam for vibration control [13,14]. In contrast to natural organisms, these structures typically contain permanently rigid materials and/or are dependent on bulky external hardware.

More recently, there has been growing interest in “soft” robotics and related technologies that are composed almost entirely of condensed soft matter [15]. Unlike conventional machines and electronics, these soft machines exhibit many of the same elastic and rheological properties of their biological tissue and organs. This mechanical similarity is essential for not only biomimetic but also for mechanical “impedance” matching with human tissue for safe human-robot interaction. Whereas rigid materials can constrain natural human motion and can cause injury, soft materials preserve natural mechanics and reduce stress concentrations during impact.

In this paper, we present our recent studies in the area of soft multi-functional materials with reversibly tunable rigidity potentially for soft robotics applications. Our studies are based on on-board heating mechanism. We first fabricate composites containing low melting point alloys that can achieve rigidity tuning up to four orders of magnitude activated within tens of seconds. We then explore the potential of such a design by conducting thermal analysis of a simplified multilayered composite model. Based on results from thermal analysis, we recognize the room for improvement in terms of activation time of the design, and then come up with a novel biomimetic design. This new design enables activation on the order of a few seconds. We achieve this through engineering composites containing conductive polymers with a low glass transition temperature. The implications of these findings, and other contributing studies to artificial muscle design and soft robotics implementation are also discussed.

2 DESIGN APPROACHES FOR SOFT MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITES WITH REVERSIBLY TUNABLE RIGIDITY

2.1 Soft Matter Multilayered Composites Embedded with Low Melting Point Alloys

The first design approach to soft multifunctional composites with reversibly tunable rigidity is an extension to the previous multilayered composites [11,12]. However, instead of using only one thermally active layer to tune the coupling with adjacent rigid layers, we only use soft or rigidity-tuning materials. The composite is activated with an onboard Joule heater composed of an acrylic elastomer (VHB™ tape; 3M) embedded with serpentine channels filled with liquid-phase eutectic gallium indium (EGaIn) or gallium-indium-tin (Galinstan) metal alloy (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: (a) Fabrication of a soft heater Galinstan heating element embedded in an acrylic VHB elastomer: (left) VHB film and liner are patterned with a laser engraver and bonded to a VHB substrate; (middle) sample is coated with Galinstan, which wets the exposed portions of the substrate; (right) the liner mask is removed and the patterned surface is sealed with a VHB film. (b) Liquid-phase Galinstan heater embedded in VHB elastomer. (Ref. [16]. © IOP Publishing. Reproduced with permission. All rights reserved.)

Details of the fabrication process are presented in Ref. [16]. We begin by producing the elastic Joule heating element using the steps shown in Fig. 1a. A 30 W CO₂ laser engraver (VLS 3.50; Universal Laser Systems) is used pattern the heater geometry in a sheet of VHB tape and liner film.

After removing the excess tape and liner, we bond the patterned sheet to a second layer of VHB tape. Next, we deposit liquid Galinstan, and remove the liner mask, leaving liquid alloy only in the exposed surface features. Lastly, we attach copper shim wires and seal the liquid by bonding a third layer of VHB tape. As shown in Fig. 1b, this method allows a Galinstan heater to be embedded in a thin sheet of VHB elastomer. Since the alloy is liquid at room temperature, the heater can be stretched to several times its natural length without losing electrical functionality.

As shown in Fig. 2, the composite contains both the stretchable Joule heating element and a thermally-responsive rigidity tuning layer. It can be represented as a five-layer structure, including the insulating layer between the top and bottom sealing layers of VHB acrylic elastomer. The thermal responsive layer can be fabricated using the same fabrication methods as the soft heater. Instead of a liquid metal alloy at room temperature, we use Field's metal (RotoMetals, Inc.), which is a low melting point alloy with a melting point of 62 °C. This way, the fabrication steps described earlier can be simply carried out on a hot plate. At room temperature, the rigidity tuning composite is rigid and can support external tensile or flexural load. When electrically activated, the Field's metal is melted by the heat generated from the onboard heating element and the composite softens. As shown in Fig. 2b, the composite bends under light force.

Figure 2: (a) Stiffness tunable composite embedded with Field's metal and a liquid Galinstan heater. (b) When electrically activated, the composite softens and easily deforms. (c) Illustration of the composite, which contains a (top) elastomer sealing layer, (middle) liquid-phase Joule heating element, and (bottom) thermally activated layer of Field's metal or SMP. (d) Close-up of the Galinstan heating element; ruler marks spaced 1 mm apart. (Ref. [16]. © IOP Publishing. Reproduced with permission. All rights reserved.)

Using tensile testing, we characterize the rigidity change of the composite to reversibly change between approximately 1 GPa and 100 kPa. Based on tests with several composite samples, we measured an activation time on the order of tens of seconds. If we replace the Field's metal layer with a SMP layer, the effective rigidity change is less and the activation time does not significantly change. Details of the results are presented in Ref. [16].

2.2 Thermal Analysis of Multilayered Rigidity Tunable Composite

Although promising, the composite presented in Sec. 2.1 represents an early prototype with an *ad*

hoc selection of materials and dimensions. Further improvements to power consumption and activation time would benefit from a theoretical model that can inform design decisions. We address this with a simplified 1D model presented in Fig. 3 and described in Ref. [17]. Using this simplified model, we conduct a thermal analysis using both analytical and numerical techniques.

Figure 3: 1D model of the rigidity tunable composite for a transient thermal analysis of the activation process. (Reprinted from Ref. [17] with permission from Elsevier. © Elsevier 2013)

Figure 4: Predicted activation time of RTC using various thermally responsive materials and elastomers depending on power input. (Reprinted from Ref. [17] with permission from Elsevier. © Elsevier 2013)

The governing equation for the activation process is the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \kappa(x) \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x^2} + g(x, t) &= \rho(x) C_p(x) \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t}, \quad (x \in [0, L]) \\
 \theta_{inter^-} &= \theta_{inter^+}, \\
 k_{inter^-} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} \Big|_{inter^-} &= k_{inter^+} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} \Big|_{inter^+}, \\
 \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} - h_{air} \theta \right) \Big|_{x=0} &= 0, \\
 \left(-\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} - h_{air} \theta \right) \Big|_{x=L} &= 0, \\
 \theta(x, 0) &= 0.
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Here $\theta(x,t)$ is the relative temperature with respect to room temperature, $\kappa(x)$ is the thermal conductivity, $\rho(x)$ is the density, $C_p(x)$ is the specific heat. Since the layers are different materials, the

physical properties are only piece-wise continuous. Eqn. (1) shows (i) the heat conduction equation (with nonzero generation $g(x,t)$) followed by the (ii) temperature and (iii) heat flux continuity condition on the internal interfaces, the convective boundary conditions on the (iv) top and (v) bottom surfaces, and the (vi) initial condition for the temperature field.

The results of the analytical and numerical agree well with each other and are also consistent with the results of tabletop experimental measurements [17]. When we consider the use of other thermally responsive materials and embedding elastomers, the modeling results show that the activation time will still be on the order of tens of seconds (Fig. 4). The main reason for this can be attributed to the additional insulating layer between where the heat is generated and absorbed. This insulating layer is needed for containing the liquid metal alloy in the soft heater but creates a barrier to thermal diffusion. This suggests that a better design based on different mechanisms for thermal activation may be required in order to achieve more rapid rigidity tuning.

2.3 Soft Matter Composites Containing Conductive Elastomer with Low Glass Transition Temperature

Recognizing the activation time limitation of the previous approach for the design of multifunctional materials with reversibly tunable rigidity, we turn to a better design addressing directly the root cause for the slow activation: the separation of where heat is generated and where heat is used for melting or glass transition. Towards this end, we combine these two processes into one component of the composite by engineering new elastomers that are conductive and exhibit a low glass transition temperature. The elimination of liquid metal alloys avoids sealing issues, in addition to extra heat dissipation and diffusion length to cross.

Figure 5: Fabrication of cPBE-PDMS composite: (i-ii) propylene-ethylene co-polymer (clear pellets) is mixed with structured carbon black to produce a conductive propylene-based elastomer (cPBE; black pellets); (iii-v). When flattened into thin sheets, the cPBE may be patterned with a CO₂ laser and embedded in PDMS. (Ref. [18]. © IOP Publishing. Reproduced with permission. All rights reserved.)

Fig. 5 shows the new rigidity tunable composite containing a conductive propylene-based elastomer (cPBE). The cPBE is produced by combining a propylene-ethylene co-polymer with a percolating network of structured carbon black. It has a weight composition of 51/9/40% propylene,

ethylene and structured carbon black. Custom-ordered pellets are supplied by THEMIX Plastics, Inc (Lake Mills, WI) and pressed between steel plates at 90 °C to form thin sheets. Flattened sheets of cPBE (step iii) are patterned with a CO₂ laser to form shapes with electrical terminals to supply current (step iv). Finally, the cPBE strip is sealed within a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) matrix. With ~0.1-1W of supplied electrical power, the effective elastic modulus of the composite reversibly changes between 1.5 and 37 MPa. This approximately corresponds to the difference in rigidity between human cartilage and skin. Thanks to its relatively low glass transition temperature at 75 °C, the activation time can be achieved within a few seconds [18].

We demonstrate one potential application of this rigidity tunable composite in a soft pneumatic finger. Referring to Fig. 6, three cPBE-PDMS strips are aligned on the sidewall of the finger symmetrically. When selectively activating one of the strips, the rigidity of the corresponding segment of the finger wall decreases and exhibits greater expansion. This results in the finger bending in the opposite. This clearly shows the potential of the integration of such materials into soft robotics and wearable devices applications.

Figure 6: (a) Soft pneumatic robot finger integrated with cPBE “tendons” and a single air supply. (b) at rest, not inflated and not activated (c-d) the finger bends in different directions depending on which tendon element is activated to allow for stretch. (Ref. [18]. © IOP Publishing. Reproduced with permission. All rights reserved.)

3 CONCLUDING REMARKS AND PERSPECTIVES

In this manuscript, we present our recent efforts in the area of soft multifunctional materials with reversibly tunable rigidity. We focus on direct Joule heating by passing electrical current through an embedded conductive element. We first use low melting point alloys and shape memory polymer as the thermal responsive materials. When bonded to a liquid-phase metal alloy heater, we are able to achieve up to four orders of magnitude of reversible change in rigidity. While promising, these early prototypes require ~10-100s for activation with ~6W of supplied power. To reduce the activation time and power consumption, we perform a transient thermal analysis on a 1D model of the multi-layered composite. Based on the results of the thermal analysis, we conclude that the inefficiency of the heat generation and diffusion fundamentally limits the performance of the rigidity tunable composite. We then introduce an improved design composed of a conductive thermoplastic elastomer with a low glass transition temperature. This composite exhibits a reduced activation time of ~2-5 seconds, which is an order of magnitude improvement when compared with the first approach using low melting point alloys and shape memory polymer.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) Young Faculty Award (Grant no. N66001-12-1-4255). The authors hereby would also like to acknowledge the helpful discussions with Mr. Steven Kidd from THEMIX Plastics, Inc, in manufacturing of cPBE.

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